

ADAPTATION OF A EARLY CHILD TO A PRESCHOOL INSTITUTION

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Abstract: In the article, the author analyzes the concepts of "adaptation" and types of adaptation, and provides recommendations for optimizing the process of adaptation of young preschool children to the conditions of a preschool educational organization.

Keywords: adaptation, young preschool children, preschool educational organization.

At the present stage of development of independent Uzbekistan, the problem of adaptation of a child to a preschool institution is extremely urgent.

The term "adaptation" (from Latin Adaptatio - adaptation, adjustment) means the ability of an organism to adjust to various conditions of the external environment. We are interested in the psychological aspects of the problem of adaptation. Social adaptation is the adaptation of a person to the conditions of a new social environment; one of the socio-psychological mechanisms of socialization of an individual. In pedagogical practice, it is important to take into account the peculiarities of the process of adaptation of a child to the changed conditions of his life and activity upon entering public educational institutions (kindergarten, school), upon joining a new team.

The concept of "adaptation" in its broadest definition means the correspondence between a living system and external conditions, and adaptation is both a process and a result, i.e. a certain organization. From a physiological point of view, adaptation is a restructuring of an internal dynamic stereotype depending on changes in external conditions. According to I.P. Pavlov, external living conditions, the external environment are an external stereotype. He noted that when changing the usual way of life, when stopping habitual activities, there are violations of the old dynamic stereotype and difficulties in establishing a new one. Despite all the

existing differences in the interpretation of adaptation, the main thing is always highlighted - the universal nature of the tendency to establish equilibrium between the components of real systems. Therefore, it is no coincidence that over time, the concept of "adaptation" moved into functional, and then into social psychology.

Jean Piaget made the most important contribution to the development of the concept of "adaptation". Adaptation, according to J. Piaget, ensures a balance between the impact of the organism on the environment and the reverse impact of the environment or, which is the same thing, balance in the interaction of the subject and the object. It was J. Piaget who, in his concept, first began to consider the relationship of a person with the social microenvironment as a homeostatic equilibration, transferring the concept of "homeostasis" from the organism to the personality.

In the works of Russian psychologists, the theory of adaptation is further developed. Thus, A.N. Leontiev, referring to the concept of J. Piaget, objected to the "unconditional, inappropriate analysis" of the spread of the concept of "homeostasis" (in the meaning of "adaptation") to the ontogenetic development of man. Indeed, human adaptation to the conditions of existence is fundamentally different from the adaptive behavior of animals, has greater flexibility and ingenuity. The process of human adaptation to reality occurs under the control of consciousness.

Moreover, each person, due to their individual psychological characteristics (type of nervous system, life experience, etc.), has individual adaptive mechanisms, and, consequently, their own type of adaptation. In the works of Russian psychologists and teachers, the theory of child adaptation in preschool institutions was developed by Sh.A. Sadykova, and in schools - N.Kh. Rakhmankulova.

A necessary condition for successful adaptation is the coordination of the actions of parents and educators. Even before the child enters the group, educators should establish contact with the family. According to K. L. Pechora (1998), only 18.2% of children are ready to attend a preschool institution, 6% are not ready, and 81.2% are conditionally ready. In this regard, the process of getting used to a preschool institution does not always go smoothly and is accompanied by illnesses of children. It is rare to meet parents who, as the moment approaches when their child must go to a nursery or kindergarten, do not experience anxiety. How will the baby be received? What kind of relationship will he have with the teacher? Will he

often get sick? Most of the worries are connected with how quickly the child will get used to and adapt to the new environment. This anxiety has real grounds, since it is known that changes in the social environment affect both the mental and physical health of children. From this point of view, special attention is required at an early age, when many children first move from a closed family world to a world of broad social contacts. If a three-year-old child preparing for kindergarten already has speech, some self-care skills, has experience communicating with adults and feels the need for children's company, then a one-and-a-half to two-year-old child is less adapted to separation from his family, weaker and more vulnerable. It is at this age that adaptation takes longer and is more difficult, often accompanied by illnesses. During this period, intensive physical development and the maturation of all mental processes occur. Being at the stage of formation, the child is most susceptible to fluctuations and even breakdowns. Changing environmental conditions and the need to develop new forms of behavior require certain efforts and skills on the part of the child, causing the emergence of a stage of intense adaptation. The extent to which the child is prepared in the family for the transition to a child care institution determines both his adaptation to the nursery (which can last for six months) and his further development. A system of medical and pedagogical assistance to children entering nurseries is being developed. It includes work with parents aimed at strengthening the physical health of children, linking the daily routine at home with the conditions of the new environment. In order to facilitate the adaptation period, it is recommended to gradually include the child in the nursery group, create a special emotional climate for him. The main concern here is the prevention of children's illnesses and the reduction of their emotional discomfort during the adaptation period. However, these measures alleviate the already existing serious condition, but do not affect the causes that give rise to it. At the same time, it is clear that it is much more important to organize child care and upbringing in the family in such a way as to minimize complications of the adaptation period. There is no doubt that the causes of complications in the physical and mental state of children are, first of all, psychological in nature and are in the sphere of social relations of the child with the outside world. This is recognized by doctors, teachers and psychologists. Therefore, our goal is to study the psychological aspects of a child's adaptation to a children's institution. The following factors influence the nature of the child's adaptation:

1) the level of mental development of the child; 2) the relationship of the child with the mother.

Adaptation is the adjustment of the body to a new environment, and for a child, a kindergarten is undoubtedly a new, still unknown space, with a new environment and new relationships. Adaptation includes a wide range of individual reactions, the nature of which depends on the psychophysiological and personal characteristics of the child, on the established family relationships, on the conditions of stay in the preschool institution. However, naturally, there are a number of patterns that should be known for effective interaction with the child and the possibility of protecting him from strong negative stressful situations. One of the main tasks in the work of a preschool psychologist is to find conditions that can have a positive impact on the success of adaptation. Perhaps such conditions are the communication skills acquired by the child in the family. Preschool children have a number of psychological and physiological characteristics, the knowledge of which is necessary in order to truly understand the extent of the impact of the world around them on the child, to understand that their sensitivity is so great that any traumatic impact can lead to pathological consequences in the development of the child's psyche. In the formation of a child, one of the decisive places is given to the family. The child's first acquaintance with the world around him occurs through his parents, so their influence, especially maternal, is great and responsible. The character traits and the world of feelings of the child, his attitude to knowledge and the direction that his development as a person and his life path will ultimately take will depend on the family atmosphere. The problem of family education is now more acute than ever before for our society and its solution will largely predetermine its future. Today, it is extremely important to consider the main socio-psychological phenomena: communication, interaction, interpersonal relationships in a group of preschool children, which is one of the most important in the process of socialization and adaptation of the child.

Knowing the relationship between the communication skills acquired by the child in the family and the nature of adaptation allows the psychologist to predict the success of the adaptation process and organize preventive work with children planning to enter a preschool institution.

Although kindergartens now accept children of an even younger age, the most favorable age is between 3 and 5 years. Prepare your child in advance for the idea

of kindergarten, for the need to attend it. And the first thing you need to do is - about a month before he starts going there - be less than usual near him. Secondly, tell him in detail about the kindergarten, take him there so that he finds out what it is, and he forms his own idea of it. Tell the child that you are very proud of him - after all, he is already so big that he can go to kindergarten himself. But do not make a problem out of this event, do not talk every day about the upcoming change in his life. Prepare the child for communication with other children and adults: visit children's parks and playgrounds with him, accustom him to playing in sandboxes, on swings. Go with him to holidays, to friends' birthdays, observe how he behaves: is he shy, secluded, conflicts, fights or easily finds a common language, contacts with peers, is drawn to communication, is relaxed. Some children get very tired in kindergarten in the first days from new impressions, new friends, new activities, a large number of people. If the child comes home exhausted and nervous, this does not mean that he is not able to get used to kindergarten. Perhaps it is necessary to pick up such a child from kindergarten earlier or leave him at home 1-2 times a week.

- There are three types of adaptation:

- **favorable** - the psycho-emotional status is from + 13 points to + 49 (the points on the adaptation sheet are calculated by medical workers in the kindergarten), health group - 1, 2, no diagnoses of a neurological nature, anemia, delayed speech development, diathesis;

- **conditionally favorable** - the psycho-emotional status is from - 20 points to + 13, health group - 2, 3, diagnoses of a neurological nature, anemia, delayed speech development, diathesis;

- **unfavorable** - the psycho-emotional status is from - 20 points to - 59, health group - 2, 3, diagnoses of a neurological nature, anemia, delayed speech development, diathesis.

- Adaptation is complete if:

- the child has a stable positive psycho-emotional state for a week, i.e. Your child is generally in a good mood, plays actively, interacts with adults and peers, follows a daily routine, eats well and sleeps peacefully;

- the child has no illnesses;

- body weight dynamics are noted;

- psychomotor development dynamics are noted.

However, the most important condition for successful adaptation of not so much the child, but the whole family is the parents' readiness for the child to go to kindergarten (public or private), or for his living conditions to change somehow, for

example, a nanny will look after him, or for a long time the child will move in with his grandmother, etc. Consequently, it can be argued that the child's adaptation to a preschool institution serves as an important component in his further formation and development as an individual.

References:

1. Chabrova T.L., Djanpeisova G.E. Biz birga o'samiz va o'rganamiz. T.: Innovatsiya-Ziyo. 2020
2. Чаброва Т.Л. Рисуем вместе; Bekinmashoq-Plyuse-Tashkent, 2012
3. Чаброва Т.Л. Болага нима керак? ООО «Сjmprix Print» 2016.-36бет